

Analysis of Effect of Long Term Financing on Profitability of Supermarkets in Central Business District Nairobi City Kenya

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Abstract: *The research aim was to examine the effect of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya. The study was based on pecking order theory. The study adopted a cross-sectional explanatory research design. The study focused on 18 major supermarkets in Nairobi central business district Kenya. The target population was 18 branch supervisors and 18 accountants of major supermarkets in Nairobi central business district Kenya. The study utilized a census approach. Structured questionnaires were utilized to gather primary statistics from the respondents and secondary data were obtained from the annual corporate financial statements of selected supermarkets in Nairobi central business district. Data were evaluated by the use of descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistical analysis. The statistics gathered were dissected using regression analysis with the support of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) model 22. The relationship between long-term financing and profitability was assessed using Pearson's correlation and multiple regression analysis. The study revealed that the long-term financing correlation coefficient was positive and significant ($r=0.590^{**}$, $P<0.000$). Further revealed that long-term financing positively influenced the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city. The study concluded that long-term financing had a positive and statistically significant effect on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya. The study recommends that management of the supermarkets should emphasize the need to make the ideal decisions that include increased long-term funding that will assist with expanding supermarket profitability, additionally, they should introduce strategies like a mix of equity and debt that will decrease the cost of capital which will boost profitability and ensure that there is optimal capital in their operations and developments. The study recommends that the government should nurture the retail sector by forming different strategies and schemes such as debt relief finance schemes, collateral-free loans, corporate rates reliefs, business rates deferral, and tax credits schemes to help improve their capital base and cash flow.*

Keywords: Bank loan, Debenture finance, Equity finance, Profitability

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Long-term financing is an obligation that has a maturity period of over one year like bonds. It is an advance made for an organization commonly as development capital and is customarily repaid at some future period. Debt capital varies from equity capital since contributors to debt capital do not become part proprietors of the organizations but are creditors. Equity capital represents the risk capital ventured by the proprietors through the acquisition of an organization's common shares. Equity finance has linked costs that would increase to the expense of operating a business together with various bureaucratic procedures that might influence the business decisions. The optimal

financial structure is the combination of equity and debt which moderates the cost of capital of an organization and its monetary risk to the barest least to expand firm worth (Aljamaan, 2018).

Kirimi, Simiyu, and Murithi (2017) describe debt financing as the deed of corporate raising funds by over-borrowing from external sources through the dispensation of a bond, debenture, and loans. Funding an organization through commercial bank loans offers it an opportunity for growth through extension when utilized properly without influencing the organization's ownership. A debenture is a long-term liability instrument that provides its owners the right of credit against the distributing organization (Maria, 2019). Profitability is an appraisal of organization productivity and its achievement or non-performance using return on equity and return on assets. Profitability is a benchmark of the capability of supermarkets to adapt to their capital development, revealing their competitiveness and deciding the growth of a business (Hallunovi & Berdo, 2018).

Lack of sufficient long-term financing has turned into a significant and demanding issue in various evolving economies, especially since the worldwide monetary emergency of 2008-2009. Accessing long-term capital is basic since it can allow governments and organizations to fund large long-term investments and moderate rollover risks and threats. Long-term funding can be imperative for supermarkets as it empowers them to handle massive and huge investments that may be basic for their development (Peria & Schmukler, 2017).

In the lack of long-term financing, organizations may need to depend on short-term finances and their incapability to turn over short-term finances may reason an organization to decrease productive long-term projects with concerns for their development potential. Long-term finance may contribute to higher growth and lower macroeconomic volatility is critical for infrastructure projects, which by nature take many years to complete and require lumpy investments (Peria & Schmukler, 2017).

Long-term debt in the supermarket financial structures was viewed as statistically noteworthy however adversely related to profitability. Kasozi (2018) argued that the retail sector relies more on internally produced funds to produce incomes and that the retail sector is extremely leveraged with over 52% of its assets funded by debt and this adversely influences retail firms' profits.

Sufficient commercial bank loans are major to running and developing any corporate business into an effective venture. An additional investment that comes from external creditors and is utilized properly can increase the profitability of the supermarkets. Improvements in profitability are related to expanded utilization of long-term financing. Commercial sector advancement in the world and Kenya has made a massive range from which organizations can acquire capital. Organizational profitability is influenced by financial structure decisions such as securing commercial bank loans (Sembeya & Otinga, 2019).

A significant number of organizations utilize long-term debt as their cash flow to start or sustain their business. Debt is one of the essential ways to know the performance and growth of the organization. Long-term debt financing allows the manufacturing company to improve its profitability (Mamaro & Legotlo, 2020). Wrong financing decisions may delay businesses' quality performance this can accelerate a firm to face liquidation (Doan, 2020).

In this period of development and the greatest aggressive world, financing choices assume a critical role in supporting the effectiveness of the supermarkets. Long-term financing is associated with long-term expenditure in fixed assets choices. After modernization and globalization of economic strategies throughout the world, venture opportunities have extended, financing alternatives have expanded and dependence on long-term financing has improved. Long-term financing is the most desired source of debt financing among well-established supermarkets (Singh & Bagga, 2019).

Global retail markets have been encountering financial crises during the last decade which has caused supermarkets to be under pressure both globally and locally. Globalizations in the economy had made supermarket openings in developing retail in nations like India, China, Brazil, and Russia countries (Cherono, 2017). Globally, a critical factor in retail sector growth and investment is financing. Development in the retail sector involves a huge expenditure of fiscal assets therefore access to inexpensive and sufficient capital is vital. The supermarket's performance relies upon the accessibility of investment and the terms of the borrowed finances that must be reimbursed to their financial suppliers (Kang, 2015).

According to the European Central Bank report (2019), the Italian organizations announced an emergent need for bank loans and credit lines containing that the absence of acceptable access to capital determines solid limitations on industry development and concurrently increases the threat of financial distress. Long-term funds assume an essential part in endorsing organization survival and expansion. Even with support plans at the European Union access to capital remains one of the organization's strategic issues in certain Member States.

The retail trade in Australia has been challenged by several competitive challenges being a lack of sufficient capital and internet retailing which has permitted the access of new innovative international retailers which is extensive. The capital employed efficiency of the supermarkets and grocery stores sector in Australia had reliably improved from 2016 to 2019 (Van Kampen & Kirkham, 2020).

Funding decisions on retailing sector companies on Indonesia Stock Exchange were more subjective by the pecking order concept. Internal funding sources were favored to avoid high credit interest charges thus internal funding should be focused on more than external financing to evade financial distress. The supermarket sector in Indonesia is unable to access long-term capital in light of high bank interest charges. The results of the study showed that the capital structure was influenced by dynamics of profitability, corporate magnitude, liquidity, and non-debt tax shields (Sutarka et al., 2018).

In Greek retail supermarkets use diverse strategies to realize a better return on equity-like working with much lower income margins through utilizing their assets more intensively. In Greek financial crisis has impacted the profitability of Greek retailers and specifically yield on assets. Supermarkets face high reductions in operating profit contingent to a great extent on fixed to variable expenses (Kolias & Arnis, 2019).

In Pakistani manufacturing sectors confront long-term financial constraints to accomplish their investment needs owing to the high inflation and interest cost, import-based economy, lower foreign speculation, exchange rate instability, and taxes. Manufacturing organizations generally choose long-term financing which has consequences associated with the organization's profitability (Sheikh & Qureshi, 2017).

In Brazil, the issuance of debentures is one of the most significant and oldest funding ways through fixed income securities. Brazilian organizations depend on debentures as an essential fundraising source investment that enhances their performance (Maria, 2019). In Romania, a study by Carstea et al. (2017) indicated that debts and stocks affect the net profit of the supermarkets while the capital and long-term assets do not show a major role in determining profitability in the retail sector.

In Africa, access to debt finance is the main constraint to supermarkets that prevents them from attaining their objectives and furthermore restricts the development of aspirational objectives for the African countries at large. Access to debt finance is one of the components that stimulate supermarkets to improve profitability. In Tanzania, organizations choose external financing from financial institutions as it is essential for them for endurance and operations. Thus, the public authority of Tanzania has dispatched strategies and projects to enable organizations with improved financial products that are custom-made to their requirements (Mori, 2018).

In Nigeria, retail goods firms depend on long-term debt which emphatically influences their performance. Further Jones and Edwin (2019) argued that there is a need for Nigerian firms to depend less on short-term debts which form a significant portion of their leverage and emphasis more on developing internal strategies that can help improve their performance (Jones & Edwin, 2019).

According to Euro monitor International (2017), the South African retail sector has been encountering a decrease in sales and incomes due to the growing international competition and a drop in investor and consumer assurance. Retail firms in South Africa depend on internal sources of funding as opposed to long-term debt since it's economical, whereas long-term debt entails a commitment to make repayment. South African retail firms avoid utilizing long-term finances to finance their operation as repaying is expensive compared to short-term financing and internal financings (Mamaro & Legotlo, 2020).

In Tanzania, well-structured multinational supermarket branches move in traditional retail markets with all the advantages of outstanding economies of scale and innovative technology. Long-term financing is the most imperative resource that increases the performance of the supermarket in Tanzania (Mohamed, 2019).

In Uganda study conducted by Namukwaya (2019) showed that the supermarkets face low profitability, liquidity crisis, and worse competitive capacity, increased assets employed in risk capital, and a lack of capacity to unlock long-term financing to back development.

Kenya is the second-leading retail sector on the continent, behind South Africa having a critical impact on the country's economy contributing over 6.3% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2018 according to the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. The development in the retail sector has been strong and distinguished as one of the sectors projected to contribute the major portion of Kenya's GDP in the country's financial plan Vision 2030 (Kimotho, 2017).

Kenya's retail sector has constantly been experiencing contingencies ensuing in the collapse of strategic supermarkets like Shoprite, Deacons, Tuskys, Choppies, Nakumatt, and Uchumi. The imperfect of this sector has left various supermarkets struggling with creditors and supplier's distress that threatens to overturn the supermarkets (Cytonn Investments, 2019).

In Nakuru town a study by Cheruyot and Wahome (2019) concluded that the debt-equity ratio has a significant influence on financial distress management in supermarkets in Nakuru town, further, they established that the debt-equity ratio had a favorable significant association with financial distress management. Hence, an optimal debt-equity ratio goes a long way in determining success in financial distress management in supermarkets.

Capital challenges amongst supermarkets particularly in Nairobi city have left them on the edge of downfall. The failure by the supermarket to settle obligation commitments prompts bankruptcy issues and prevents financial sustainability. Accumulation of debts by supermarkets without perfect structures to balance them is also a key signal of ineffective liquidity management. The incapability to settle an obligation is a great monetary sustainability challenge among supermarkets in Kenya (Mwangi & Muturi, 2018).

The incapability to generate cash flow quickly adequate to pay suppliers has placed supermarkets in a risky spot and the possibility of becoming bankrupt is gradually approaching faster to actuality. Poor performance by supermarkets in Kenya specifically Nairobi County is due to disorganized corporate governance practices and monetary limitations identified with quick development and weak sales capacity. The financial constraints due to growing suppliers' debts and rent arrears have seen significant supermarkets in Nairobi such as Uchumi, Nakumatt, Ukwala, Choppies, and Tuskys shutting their outlets and even exiting the Kenyan market absolutely in the year 2018 (Cytonn Investments, 2018). Therefore research seeks to assess the effect of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Kenya is the second-leading retail sector on the continent, behind South Africa having a critical impact on the country's economy contributing over 6.3% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2018 according to the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. Kenya is the fastest-developing retail market in Africa and per capita, spending on groceries is projected to increase to US\$330 by 2020. The development in the retail sector has been strong and distinguished as one of the sectors projected to contribute the major portion of Kenya's GDP in the country's financial plan Vision 2030 (Kimotho, 2017).

In 2019, the Kenyan retail sector's performance fell marginally with average rental incomes of 7.0% in 2019 lower than the 8.6% registered in 2018. Several supermarkets also encountered a reduction in their profit margins and credit consumers were slower to repay obligations. Kenya's retail sector has constantly been experiencing contingencies ensuing in the collapse of the strategic supermarkets like Shoprite, Deacons, Tuskys, Choppies, Ukwala, Nakumatt, and Uchumi. The imperfect of this sector has left various supermarkets struggling with creditors and suppliers distress that threatens to overturn the supermarkets. In 2018 supermarkets in Nairobi faced financial constraints and recorded poor performance due to growing suppliers' debts and rent arrears which saw significant supermarkets like Tuskys, Choppies, Ukwala, Nakumatt, and Uchumi shutting their outlets in 2018 (Cytonn Investments, 2018).

In light of the above, the government has employed several strategies such as tax incentives and credit, loan discounts, and financial literacy which were aimed at enhancing the profitability of supermarkets. Despite successive strategies interventions supermarket has continued experiencing poor performance and poor profitability which has prompted the collapse of more supermarket. Hence there is an alarming necessity for research such as the current one to determine the causes of poor performance of supermarkets in Nairobi City County where the supermarket has been performing poorly.

Although several studies have been performed on long-term financings, like in Kenya, Cheruyot and Wahome (2019) examined the impact of debt-equity proportion on management of financial distress in supermarkets in Nakuru city Kenya, Omollo, Muturi, and Wanjare (2018) analyzed the impacts of debt financing and monetary performance of non-financial corporations registered on the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Lokwang, Gichure, and Oteki (2018) determined effect of retained profits and performance of supermarkets in Trans Nzoia County in Kenya, Kimathi (2019) explored the impact of debt financing and financial performance of public universities in Kenya. Regionally Mulema (2019) studied on long-term financing and development of Small and Medium Enterprises in Uganda and Kasozi (2018) investigated whether the capital structure practices of registered retail corporations in South Africa influence their profitability. Globally Risfandy (2018) investigated equity financing and profitability of Islamic banks in Indonesia biggest Muslim country, Wahyudi, Mujibatun, and Riduwan (2019) studied debt and equity-based financing; size, and Islamic banks profitability in Indonesia and Zhang, Zhang and Guo (2019) assessed the effects of equity financing and debt financing on technological innovation: Evidence from industrialized countries.

The above studies were carried out across diverse sectors and geographic contexts and various long-term financing variables were utilized. The above research presented incompatible outcomes concerning the relationship between long-term financing and profitability. Further studies established that long-term financing had a positive and adverse influence on profitability and was done in developed nations and their conclusion are generally inconsistent. It is therefore apparent that past exploration has not addressed the influences of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in Nairobi city Kenya. It is against this background that this study seeks to fill this gap by determining the effect of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in central business district Nairobi city Kenya.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To examine the effect of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1.1 PECKING ORDER THEORY

The theory of Pecking order was first recommended by Donaldson (1961) and was modified by Myers and Majluf in 1984. The pecking order theory expresses that companies focus on their sources of financing from internal financing to equity and consider equity financing as a last alternative. This theory upholds that companies adhere to a hierarchy of financing sources and desire internal financing when accessible, and debt is preferred over equity if external funding is recommended. A corporation is held to follow a pecking order concept if it prefers internal to external financing and debt to equity if external financing is utilized. According to the pecking order theory in the existence of asymmetric information, a corporation will prefer internal finance however would issue debt if internal finance was expended (Myers & Majluf, 1984).

The theory advocates that organizations have a certain preference order of raising capital starting with less risky retained incomes, then safe debt, and lastly equity. This proposes that for organizations to improve on their cash flows and increase returns they need to pursue a particular hierarchical technique of funding their operations beginning with the least-cost source of retained incomes, safe debt, and lastly equity. The pecking order hypothesis accepts that there is no target capital structure. The organizations determine capitals according to the following preference order that is internal finance, external finance such as debt, equity. The theory proposes that profitable organizations would probably be funded by internal sources and this clarifies why they have fewer debts in their financial structures (Myers & Majluf, 1984).

According to Sin, Chen, Tze, and Boon (2017) the pecking order theory clarifies that there are expenses for external funding therefore corporations should utilize internal resources to get funding before considering external resources. A higher debt increment for more proficient tasks should be possible assuming internal funding sources are no longer capable to meet all of the organization's operative activities. The pecking order theory describes that organization management will utilize very sources of capital such as debt and capital so that operative activities can continue.

Wanja (2017) established very strong support for the pecking order theory among organizations in Kenya and that Kenyan organizations do follow the pecking order hypothesis in their capital structure decisions. This implies that organizations recognize the expenses of information related to debt and equity. To reduce such expenses, they opt for retained earnings foremost, followed by debt, and lastly equity as the last alternative source.

Onatca (2019) observed that organizations in Turkey primarily use internal funds whereas external funds are utilized only when internal funds are limited. The results of the analysis showed that these organizations' approaches are fit with the pecking order theory.

Kadek (2019) revealed that asset structure, firm size, and profitability significantly affected capital structure based on pecking order theory approach. The study concluded that profitability is the determinant factor of capital structure of non-financial firms in Indonesia based on the pecking order theory approach.

2.2 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

2.2.1 LONG-TERM FINANCING AND PROFITABILITY.

In Indonesia, Wahyudi, Mujibatun, and Riduwan (2019) studied debt and equity-based financing: Size, and Islamic bank's profitability from 2008-2017. The study sampled 13 Sharia commercial banks. The regression analysis model was utilized to assess the relationship between debt and equity-based financing and profitability. The review indicated that debt and equity-based financing influence banks' profitability and debt-based financing had an adverse and significant influence on profitability. Equity-based financing had an insignificant influence on profitability.

In India, Mittal and Madan (2018) assessed the impact of financing patterns on the profitability of E-startups organizations. The study used the panel statistics regression models to estimate the relationships. The outcome of the review showed that long-term debt and short-term debt were adversely correlated with profitability while equity was positively related to profitability.

Zhang, Zhang, and Guo (2019) assessed the effects of equity financing and debt financing on technological innovation: Evidence from industrialized countries. The aim of the research was to contrast the impacts of equity financing and debt financing on high-tech innovation using a sample of 35 developed countries from 1996 to 2015. The review utilized a panel econometric model to analytically examine the relationship between equity financing and debt financing. The study revealed that equity financing positively impacts technological innovation than debt financing in terms of both financial uptrend and financial downtrend.

Among Islamic banks in Indonesia's biggest Muslim country, Risfandy (2018) investigated the equity financing and profitability of Islamic banks. The review involved a sample of 9 Islamic banks in Indonesia from 2009 to 2014. The review used an econometric model to test the relationship between equity financing and profitability. The review found that equity financing adversely influenced the profitability of Islamic banks in Indonesia.

In Nigeria, Jones and Edwin (2019) explored the influence of debt financing on the corporate performance of registered consumer goods corporations from 2006 to 2017. The study utilized 180 corporations from 15 consumer goods corporations registered on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The regression model was applied to estimate the relationship between debt financing and corporate performance. The study revealed that total obligation, long-term debt, and short-term debt to asset proportions positively influenced the performance of consumer goods corporations in Nigeria.

Among registered retail corporations in South Africa, Kasozi (2018) investigated whether the capital structure practices of these corporations influence their profitability. A panel data approach and three regression estimators were

applied. The examined population was 16 retail corporations registered on the Johannesburg Securities Exchange during the period 2008-2016. The study revealed that short-term debt, long-term debt, and total debt negatively affected the profitability of retail corporations registered on the Johannesburg Securities Exchange.

In Rwanda, Rubunda, Namusonge, and Oluoch (2019) investigated the influence of retained earnings and equity finance structure on the growth of small and medium manufacturing enterprises. A mixed exploration design was utilized for gathering and examining quantitative statistics. The study used a sample size of 273 SMEs listed on the Rwanda development board. Multiple regression review was also used to explore the relationship between retained earnings finance structure, equity finance structure, and growth of SMEs. The study concluded that equity finance structure had a significant and positive influence on the growth of small and medium manufacturing enterprises in Rwanda while retained earning finance structure was viewed as inconsequential.

John (2018) researched on equity financing and performance of hotels in Wakiso region of Lake Victoria hotel at Entebbe in Uganda from 2013-2016. The review employed 80 respondents. Pearson's correlation coefficient and the regression review were utilized to evaluate the relationship between equity financing and performance. The study revealed that equity financing is strongly and positively related to the performance of Lake Victoria Hotel at Entebbe in Uganda.

Utilizing descriptive research design Mulema (2019) studied long-term financing and development of small and medium enterprises in Uganda: A case study of MPK Graphics. The investigation utilized Pearson correlation, and regression analysis to assess the connection and impact between long-term financing and development. The review established that long-term financing positively influenced the development of SMEs in Uganda, further there was a positive connection between financial performance and the development of SMEs in Uganda.

In Kenya, Kimathi (2019) explored the impact of debt financing and the financial performance of public universities in Kenya for a period of five years 2014-2018. Descriptive analysis design and multiple linear regression were applied to assess the relationship between debt financing and financial performance. The review concluded a favorable relationship between debt financing and the financial performance of public universities in Kenya.

Research led by Abdulrehman and Nyamute (2018) on the impact of mortgage financing on the monetary performance of commercial banks in Kenya from 2007-2016. The review involved 27 commercial banks in Kenya offering mortgage funding. The correlation and regression survey were led to assess the relationship between mortgage financing and financial performance. The findings revealed that mortgage financing positively and significantly influenced the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya.

Muturi and Njeru (2019) investigated the effect of equity finance on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Kenya. The study employed a sample size of 384 registered SMEs in the designated counties by operative wholesale and retail trade. The regression and correlation analysis was used to assess the connection between equity financing and financial performance. The study revealed that equity financing favorably and significantly affected financial performance, and concluded that equity finances positively forecasted the performance of SMEs in Kenya.

Using descriptive comparative review design, Kamau (2018) assessed the moderating role of firm development rate on debt financing and financial performance of registered petroleum corporations in Kenya from 2007 to 2017. The sample size of the review was all registered petroleum corporations in the Nairobi securities exchange. The findings indicated that long-term debt, short-term debt, and total debt adversely affected financial performance. The study inferred that the debt financing of corporations prompts decreasing proceeds.

In Nakuru city Kenya, Cheruyot and Wahome (2019) examined the impact of debt-equity proportion on the management of financial distress in supermarkets. The study employed a descriptive research strategy. The target population was 182 supervision and finance officers. Statistics were examined utilizing descriptive and inferential statistics. The study established that the debt-equity ratio had a positive significant relationship with financial distress management. The study concluded that debt-equity proportion influences financial distress management in supermarkets in Nakuru city Kenya. It was established that the debt-equity ratio had a noteworthy relationship and a significant influence on financial distress management.

In Trans Nzoia County in Kenya, Lokwang, Gichure, and Oteki (2018) determined the effect of retained profits and the performance of supermarkets. The study adopted a descriptive research strategy and regression analysis to show a cause-effect relationship. The study findings indicated that there was a noteworthy connection between retained profits and the performance of supermarkets and resolved that retained income influence the performance of supermarket through reinvestment.

Mburu, Gongera, and Mwangeka (2018) assessed the influence of equity capital financing structure levels on fiscal performance of SACCOs in Kiambu County Kenya from 2013-2016. The review adopted a cross-sectional research design and a sample size of 27 SACCOs in Kikuyu Sub County Kenya. The regression and correlation examination were utilized to evaluate the connection between equity financing and financial performance. The study revealed that SACCOs' financial performance increases when there was a reduction in equity, further share capital, and retained earnings had a noteworthy impact on the financial performance of SACCO Societies in Kikuyu Sub County.

Muthoni (2019) examined the impact of equity financing on shareholder value creation of non-monetary corporations listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange for the period 2008-2014. The study employed a descriptive research design and census design of 40 non-financial corporations. The Ordinary Least Square regression review was led to observe the effect of equity financing decisions on shareholder value creation. The study established that equity financing positively affects shareholder value creation of non-monetary corporations listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange.

In Nairobi, Omollo, Muturi, and Wanjare (2018) analyzed the impacts of debt financing and monetary performance of non-financial corporations registered on the Nairobi Securities Exchange from 2009 - 2015. The study utilized ordinary least squares, fixed effects, and random effects to dissect the impacts of debt and monetary performance of 40 non-financial corporations. The study revealed that long-term debt, short-term debt, and total debt negatively and significantly impacted returns on assets, further insignificant outcomes were held in fixed-effects modeling debt and return on assets.

Among non-financial corporations registered at the Nairobi securities exchange in Kenya, Achieng and Muturi and Wanjare (2018) investigated the impact of equity financing choices on monetary performance. The relationship between equity financing choices and financial performance was assessed using panel econometric techniques on 40 non-financial firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange from 2009 to 2015. The outcomes of this review showed that common equity and retained earnings had a statistically significant impact on return on assets. The total equity proportion had a favorable and statistically significant impact on return on assets.

Using a quantitative research strategy, Mwenda (2018) researched on impact of debt financing and fiscal performance of registered companies on the Nairobi securities exchange from 2013-2017. The study targeted 53 registered companies. A multiple linear regression model was utilized to assess the relationship between debt financing and financial performance. The study established a positive significant correlation between debt financing and financial performance and presumed that obligation financing positively influenced the fiscal performance of registered companies in Kenya.

Shaaban and Ndirangu (2018) studied the influence of bond investment and the financial performance of insurance corporations registered at the Nairobi Securities Exchange. The study involved 6 insurance corporations registered on Nairobi Securities Exchange. The study revealed that bond investment had a noteworthy impact on financial performance and presumed that bond investment impacts the financial performance of insurance corporations registered at the Nairobi Securities Exchange.

2.3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

INDEPENDENT VARIABLEDEPENDENT VARIABLE

Figure 1: Conceptual framework
Source: Researcher (2019)

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross-sectional explanatory research design regarding realizing the study objective. The study focused on eighteen major supermarkets in Nairobi's central business district Kenya. The target population was an aggregate of 18 branch supervisors and 18 accountants of major supermarkets in Nairobi's central business district Kenya. The study utilized a census approach to select all 18 supermarkets as a sample for this review. In this review, profitability was used as the response variable while long-term financing was used as the explanatory variable. Structured questionnaires were utilized to gather primary statistics from the respondents and secondary data were obtained from the annual corporate financial statements of selected supermarkets in Nairobi central business district Kenya. Descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistical analysis were used as research examination techniques. The statistics gathered were dissected using regression analysis with the support of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) model 22. The findings attained were presented in type of graphs, figures, and tables. The relationship between long-term financing and profitability was assessed in the following regression model:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y=Profitability.

α =Constant.

β_1 =Coefficient of Long-term financing.

X_1 =Long-term financing.

ϵ =Error Term.

IV. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 EFFECT OF LONG-TERM FINANCING ON PROFITABILITY OF SUPERMARKETS

The general aim of the study was to examine the effect of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya. Respondents were requested to demonstrate their degree of agreement with the following assertions relating to long-term financing as shown in Table 1. Key: Scale 4.5-3.5 Strongly Agree, 3.4-3.0 Agree, 2.9- 2.5 Neutral, 2.4- 2.0, Disagree, and 1.9-1.0 Strongly Disagree.

Table 1: Long-Term Financing

Long Term Financing	Mean	Std. Deviation
Supermarket is financed by a debenture.	2.4	0.85
Supermarket is financed by bank loan.	4.3	0.59
Supermarket is financed by equity.	3.8	0.73
Lack of finance has led to poor profitability of the supermarket.	3.7	0.51
Have long-term financing increased profitability of supermarket.	3.6	0.71
Long-term financing directly influences the profitability of supermarket.	3.8	0.56
Average	3.6	0.66

Source: Research Data (2019)

Respondents differ that supermarkets are funded by a debenture, strongly accede that supermarkets are financed by bank loans, strongly agreed that most supermarkets are financed by equity, strongly agreed that lack of finance has led to poor profitability of the supermarket, and strongly agreed that long term financing has increased profitability of supermarket, strongly agreed that long term financing directly influences the profitability of supermarket. The result agrees with Sembeya and Otinga (2019) that improvements in profitability are related to the expanded utilization of long-term financing. Further agreed with Mamaro and Legotlo (2020) that long-term debt financing allows the manufacturing company to improve its profitability. Result agrees with Singh and Bagga (2019) that long-term financing is the most desired source of debt financing among well-established supermarkets. The finding concurs Mori (2018) that access to debt finance is one of the components that stimulate organizations to improve on profitability.

4.2 PROFITABILITY

Respondents were requested to demonstrate their degree of agreement with the following assertions relating to profitability as shown in Table 2. Key: Scale 4.5-3.5 strongly agree, 3.4-3.0 Agree, 2.9- 2.5 Neutral, 2.4- 2.0, Disagree, and 1.9-1.0 strongly disagree.

Table 2: Profitability

Profitability	Mean	Std. Deviation
Supermarket ROA has increased annually.	3.6	0.62
ROE of the supermarket has been expanding every year.	3.5	0.51
There has been growth in sales every year	3.6	0.67
Supermarkets have been enjoying expanding incomes annually.	3.7	0.70
Average	3.6	0.62

Source: Research Data (2019)

Respondents strongly acknowledged that supermarket ROA has increased annually, fully supported that ROE of the supermarket has been expanding every year, strongly agreed that there has been growth in sales every year, and strongly agreed that supermarkets have been enjoying expanding incomes annually.

4.3 CORRELATION ANALYSIS

A Pearson Correlation examination was utilized to determine the magnitude and direction of the relationship between long-term financing and profitability. The correlation assessment was directed at a 5% significance level using a two-tailed test. Table 3 showed the outcomes of the correlation analysis between long-term financing and profitability.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

		Correlations	
		Profitability	Long-term financing
Profitability	Pearson Correlation	1	.590**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	31	31
Long-term financing	Pearson Correlation	.590**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	31	31

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data (2019)

Table 3 showed the outcomes of the correlation analysis between long-term financing and profitability. Results revealed that the long-term financing correlation coefficient was positive and significant ($r=0.590^{**}$, $P<0.000$). This implies that an increase in long-term financing leads to a significant increase in the profitability of supermarkets. The results agree with Cheruyot and Wahome (2019) who established that the debt-equity ratio had a noteworthy relationship and a significant influence on financial distress management. The conclusions further validate those of Mittal and Madan (2018) that equity finance is positively related to profitability, additionally, this attested to the findings by Kimathi (2019) who concluded a favorable relationship between debt financing and the financial performance of public universities in Kenya. Result disagreed with Kasozi (2018) who revealed that short-term debt, long-term debt, and total debt negatively affected the profitability of retail corporations registered on the Johannesburg Securities Exchange. The conclusions further contradict those of Mittal and Madan (2018) that long-term debt and short-term debt were adversely correlated with profitability.

4.4.1 REGRESSION ANALYSIS

A multiple linear regression analysis was directed in assessing the magnitude of the relationship between long-term financing and profitability. The model summary is presented in Table 4 below

Table 4: Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.596 ^a	.355	.333	.612

a. Predictors: (Constant), Long term financing

Source: Research Data (2019)

The linear regression model designated $R^2 = 0.355$, which implied that 35.5% of the changes in profitability of supermarkets is explained by long-term financing whereas 64.5% of the variation in profitability of supermarkets is explained by other dynamics. The coefficient of determination R of 0.596 indicated a positive relationship between long-term financing and profitability.

4.4.2 ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

The conclusions on the analysis of variance presented in Table 5 shows that F statistic value of (F= 15.99, P-value < 0.05) this implies that the regression model was statistically significant in predicting the relationship between long term financing and profitability of supermarkets.

Table 5: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.985	1	5.985	15.990	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.854	29	.374		
	Total	16.839	30			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

b. Predictors: (Constant), Long term financing

Source: Research Data (2019)

4.4.3 REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS

The researcher conducted a regression analysis to determine the relationship between long-term financing and the profitability of supermarkets. The study established that long-term financing had a significant positive effect on profitability ($\beta = 0.708$, $p < 0.05$). The findings imply that holding the long-term financing at constant, the profitability of supermarkets would remain at 1.178. Additionally, a unit increase in long-term financing while holding other factors constant would lead to a 0.708 increase in the profitability of supermarkets. This confirmed the findings by Mulema (2019) who established that long-term financing positively influenced the development of SMEs in Uganda. The outcomes further prove those of Lokwang, Gichure, and Oteki (2018) who found that retained profits significantly influenced the performance of supermarkets in Trans Nzoia County in Kenya. Further, the result concurs with an observation by Achieng and Muturi, and Wanjare (2018) who showed that common equity and retained earnings positively and significantly affected the return on assets. The results are consistent with that of Mwenda (2018) who revealed that debt financing positively influenced the fiscal performance of registered companies in Kenya. The finding disagrees with the finding of Risfandy (2018) who concluded that equity financing adversely influenced the profitability of Islamic banks in Indonesia. Further disprove conclusion by Kamau (2018) that long-term debt, short-term debt, and total debt adversely affected financial performance.

Table 6: Regression Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.178	.762		1.546	.133
	Long-term financing	.708	.177	.596	3.999	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Research Data (2019)

The regression analysis equation is as shown below:

$$Y = 1.178 + 0.708 X_1$$

4.5 TREND ANALYSIS OF PROFITABILITY

4.5.1 TREND ANALYSIS OF ROA

The trend analysis results in Figure 2 revealed that the supermarkets in Nairobi Kenya experienced an upward trend in profitability for the period 2016-2018. The ROA has been constantly on the upward trend from 2016 to 2018, this was due to access to credit, lower borrowing rate, growth in purchasing power, and rise of the e-commerce market.

Figure 2: Trend Analysis of ROA

Source: Research Data (2019)

4.5.2 TREND ANALYSIS OF ROE

The trend analysis results in Figure 3 designated an upward trend from 2016 to 2018, however, there was consistent growth in ROE toward the end of 2017. This could have been credited to better access to credit, improvement of infrastructure, and growth in purchasing power.

Figure 3: Trend Analysis of ROE

Source: Research Data (2019)

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

5.1.1 EFFECT OF LONG-TERM FINANCING ON PROFITABILITY OF SUPERMARKETS.

The study sought to determine the influence of long-term financing on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya. Based on the findings, the study concludes that long-term financing had a positive and statistically significant effect on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city Kenya. The result of the correction analysis showed a positive and significant relationship between long-term financing and profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city. This implies that implementing more long-term financing results in to increase in the profitability of supermarkets and that increase in equity finance, debenture, and bank loan improves supermarket profitability. This high positive effect is improved by financing through bank loans and equity. The descriptive results revealed that supermarkets in Nairobi City are financed by bank loans and equity. The study also noted that lack of finance has led to poor profitability of the supermarket, further concluded that effective use of long term financing improves the profitability of supermarket and long term financing positively influences the profitability of supermarket.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the study made the following recommendations that could improve the supermarket business sector in Kenya. The study established that long-term financing had a significantly positive effect on the profitability of supermarkets in the central business district of Nairobi city, therefore, the study recommends that supermarket managers should emphasize the need to make the ideal decisions that include increased long-term funding that will assist with expanding supermarket profitability as well as development.

Further, the study recommends that appropriate advances should be utilized by the management of supermarkets to ensure the debt financing is used as an option for financing since it increases the supermarket's profitability and by taking benefit of tax shield relief. It is essential for supermarkets to expand the issue of debentures as a long-term source of funding as the debenture issue is an inexpensive option of financing as the interest to be paid to the bondholders is normally lower than the dividend.

The study revealed that long-term financing increases supermarkets' profitability, therefore the study recommended that they should utilize more levels of debt. It is therefore essential for financial organizations to develop convenient credit strategies such as low-interest finances, direct grants, and collateral-free loans that will facilitate long-term borrowing by supermarkets.

The study recommended that the management of the supermarkets should introduce strategies like a mix of equity and debt that will decrease the cost of capital which will boost profitability and ensure that there is optimal capital in their operations and development.

In accordance with the pecking order theory, an endorsement is made for supermarkets to utilize internal sources of funding first because of their low expenses before embracing external funding.

Further another potential alternative open to the supermarket is the development of common guarantee associations which are formed by a group of supermarkets that prolong collective assurances to finances allotted to the members of the association and which help supermarkets to acquire loans from financial institutions.

At the policy level, the study recommends that the government should nurture the retail sector by forming different strategies and schemes such as debt relief finance scheme, collateral-free loans, corporate rates reliefs, loan guarantee scheme, business rates deferral, tax credits scheme, and enterprise development grant to help improve their capital base and cash flow.

The Government through the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Co-operatives and Retail Trade Association of Kenya should set up a fund facility to empower the engaging banks to extend credit to supermarkets that meet the minimum requirements, further simplify the accessibility of and access to loan and equity funding, particularly long-term option

to boost trade and investment capability of supermarkets. Government support through provisional changes in tax arrangements, suspending tax penalties, corporate income tax rebates, deferment, and Value Added Tax (VAT) break aimed at revamping their cash flow.

The Ministry of Industry, Trade, and Co-operatives collaboration with the banking sector and private sector should implement measures for the retail sector such as decreasing the time expected to process credit applications, lowering the cost of borrowing, enhancing the availability of capital, giving exemptions of loan interest and deferral of tax.

The Government and Ministry of Industry, Trade, and Co-operatives should establish backing alternative financing techniques, like business angels and supermarket trade equity funds, and backing awareness-raising with regards to advantages of accessing public equity markets.

The government and financial institutions need to establish an empowering environment that can guarantee credit flow and suitable training on the supermarket management on the best way to utilize the borrowed capital through debt counseling and financial literacy.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The current study focused on significant supermarkets in Nairobi city county Kenya, future studies should cover other supermarkets in the different counties in order to compare the findings.

Since the study was delimited to the retail sector, therefore, it cannot be generalized to other sectors, future studies might extend to other sectors and industries to differentiate the results.

The current study was limited to 3 years' period from 2016 to 2018, future research can be extended by taking a long-time period like 10 years which increases the reliability of the results.

The study discovered that 64.5% of the change in the profitability of supermarkets is not explicated by long-term financing but instead by other undetermined factors. It will therefore be essential to direct a study to determine other factors.

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